

Performance of 12 lowland rice cultivars evaluated for grain yield (t ha⁻¹) and iron toxicity score (ITS) at sites with high iron toxicity (Korhogo) and low iron toxicity (Mbe), Côte d'Ivoire, 1994 wet season and 1995 dry season.

Cultivar	Korhogo				Mbe 1994 wet season Grain yield
	1994 wet season		1994 dry season		
	Grain yield	ITS ^a	Grain yield	ITS	
TOX3118-6-E2-3-2 (WITA 1)	6.7	1	5.0	2	7.6
CK4	6.1	1	5.0	2	8.3
CK73	4.9	2	4.9	3	4.2 ^b
TOX3052-41-E1-2	6.3	1	4.8	3	8.1
TOX3100-32-2-3-5 (WITA 3)	4.3	3	4.7	3	7.8
TOX3050-46-E3-3	6.0	1	4.6	3	6.2
TOX3081-36-2-3	6.2	1	4.4	3	6.0
TOX3027-43-1-E3-1-1-1	5.5	2	4.1	5	7.5
TOX3093-35-2-3-3 (WITA 2)	4.8	2	3.7	5	7.6
Suakoko 8	3.7	2	3.3	3	5.3
Bouake 189	4.7	3	2.9	7	6.5
TOX 3069-66-2-1-6	4.2	5	2.8	7	7.7
LSD (0.05)	1.1		0.8		0.8

^aBased on the *Standard evaluation system for rice* with a scale of 1-9, where 1 = growth and tillering nearly normal and 9 = almost all plants dead or dying. ^bYield was low because of bird damage.

foliage, were higher (indicating higher iron toxicity) in the dry season than in the wet season. Iron toxicity in the growing season was not observed to any significant extent at Mbe and the rice plants grew normally there.

Seasonal differences in yield were larger for susceptible cultivars such as Bouake 189 and TOX 3069-66-2-1-6 than for iron-tolerant cultivars such as CK 4, Suakoko 8, and WITA 3. The yield potentials of cultivars CK 4, WITA 1,

WITA 2, and WITA 3 were clearly expressed in the 1994 wet season experiment at Mbe (see table). The iron-toxicity susceptible cultivars Bouake 189 and TOX 3069-66-2-1-6 yielded 6.5 and 7.7 t ha⁻¹, respectively, at Mbe.

These results indicate that iron toxicity, coupled with dry-season environmental conditions at Korhogo, reduces the grain yield of both iron-toxicity-tolerant and -susceptible cultivars. The high temperatures in the dry season affect crop physiology, especially during grain maturity. High temperature may also enhance transpiration rates of rice plants, which could cause a higher uptake of iron. It is also known that in a growing medium where iron in solution is high (which is expected in the dry season because of the high prevailing temperatures), iron uptake increases with higher transpiration rates because of a passive uptake mechanism. In addition, water supplied by rainfall in the rainy season would dilute the iron in a soil solution and could provide some relief from iron toxicity. ■

Correlation of some varietal characteristics with grain yield and stress tolerance index under saline conditions

L. M. González and R. Ramírez, Nuclear Laboratory of the Agricultural Research Institute "Jorge Dimitrov," Gaveta Postal 2360, Bayamo 85100, Granma, Cuba

Rice production in saline soils could be increased if salt-tolerant genotypes were developed, but progress toward combining superior tolerance with good yield potential is slow, largely because of the nonavailability of reliable and efficient selection criteria. Selecting directly for grain yield under saline conditions may be limited by the low heritability of observed variation and failure to distinguish between yield potential and capacity to cope with adverse stress factors.

We evaluated the correlation of 26 characteristics with grain yield and stress tolerance index (average grain yield under stress in relation to the corresponding controls taken as one) in rice under saline conditions to ascertain the role of these traits in indirect selection for yielding ability under these conditions and in measuring varietal ratings.

We studied 20 rice varieties under laboratory conditions and in the field. In petri dishes with NaCl at electrical conductivity of 12 dS m⁻¹ (stress) and distilled water (0.02 dS m⁻¹ as a control), 30 seeds of each genotype were placed in petri dishes with filter paper, with four replications. After 48 h, seed water uptake, peroxidase, catalase, alpha, beta, and total amylase isozyme activity in germinating seeds, seed respiration, and seed redox potential were evaluated. After 7 d, seed germination, seedling height, root length, fresh and

dry weight of seedlings, leaf respiration, total water content, relative leaf water content, transpiration, sap cell concentration, proline content, and total chlorophyll content were measured. In the field, the genotypes were sown in specially designed 3 m × 3 m × 1 m test plots in saline soil (9 dS m⁻¹) and in nonstress productive soil over three seasons. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Normal cultural practices were followed. We collected data on agronomic attributes (plant height, panicles plant⁻¹, panicle length and weight, filled grains panicle⁻¹, and grain yield) from 10 plants selected at random in each replication. We computed the correlation coefficient of all traits estimated.

Seed water uptake, peroxidase activity, seed germination, seedling height, root length, seedling dry weight, total water content, and

Correlation of some characteristics of rice varieties grown in saline conditions with grain yield and saline stress index.

Characteristic	Correlation with	
	Grain yield	Saline stress tolerance index
Seed water uptake	0.47*	0.51*
Peroxidase	0.42*	0.69*
Catalase	0.15	0.36
Alpha amylase	0.10	0.11
Beta amylase	0.02	0.15
Total amylase	0.47*	0.15
Seed respiration	-0.18	0.28
Seed redox potential	0.02	0.15
Seed germination	0.68**	0.57*
Seedling height	0.71**	0.72**
Root length	0.62**	0.78**
Seedling fresh weight	0.05	0.26
Seedling dry weight	0.63**	0.66**
Leaf seedling respiration	0.29	0.30
Total water content	0.46*	0.65**
Relative leaf water content	0.57*	0.62**
Transpiration	0.05	0.04
Sap cell concentration	0.02	0.01
Proline content	0.21	0.39
Total chlorophyll content	0.25	0.29
Plant height	0.80***	0.83***
Panicles plant ⁻¹	0.30	0.29
Panicle length	0.32	0.40
Panicle weight	0.81***	0.83***
Filled grains panicle ⁻¹	0.33	0.30
1000-grain weight	0.73**	0.38

* = significant at P=0.05, ** = significant at P=0.01, and *** = significant at P=0.001.

relative leaf water content were highly correlated with the saline stress tolerance index (see table), indicating that measuring varietal ratings for salt tolerance at the early stage of growth via these traits was likely to be effective.

At the late stage of growth, plant height and panicle weight correlated highly and significantly with grain yield under saline conditions, as well as with the saline stress tolerance index, showing that varietal evaluation and indirect selection for grain yield in saline soil via these traits would be an even better method. ■

Multiple submissions. Normally, only one report for a single experiment will be accepted. Two or more items about the same work submitted at the same time will be returned for merging. Submitting at different times multiple notes from the same experiment is highly inappropriate. Detection will result in the rejection of all submissions on that research.

Integrated germplasm improvement — upland

Altamirano, Mandisovi, and Quebracho: new rice cultivars from Argentina

J. J. Marassi, A. A. Vidal, and R. Bezus, Rice Program, Facultad de Ciencias Agrarias y Forestales, Universidad Nacional de La Plata, C.C. 31 (1900), Buenos Aires, Argentina

Altamirano P.A. is, because of its growth duration, tolerance for low temperatures, and good performance on saline and alkaline soils, recommended for sowing in temperate zones or under these soil limitations, according to the new aims of our rice program.

This variety is 0.98 m tall, resists lodging, and has intermediate threshability. It reaches maturity in 133 d and its yield potential is 8,000 kg ha⁻¹. The caryopsis is 7.47 mm long and 2.79 mm wide and the ratio of length to width is 2.67, matching that of the commercial type.

Its endosperm has a medium amylose content (21%) and an intermediate gelatinization temperature. Its protein content is 8.35%. It is moderately resistant to *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav.

This variety originated from the cross of experimental line H-115-19-1 and variety Yerua P.A. to obtain the highest quality of grain, yield, and *P. grisea* Cav. resistance. Line H-115-19-1 came from the cross of varieties Dawn and Zenith. Crossing was carried out by the rice program at the Ing. Agr. Julio Hirschhorn Experiment Station. A combination of mass and pedigree selection was used.

Because of its earliness, Altamirano was released for cultivation in areas near 30 °S in Buenos Aires Province.

Mandisovi P.A. was bred to satisfy the demand for aromatic rices, which, unlike La Calendaria FA, has a caryopsis that corresponds to the long-wide type. It can be consumed both as polished or integral rice (this alone or mixed with red pericarp rice).

Mandisovi is 0.83 m tall, resists lodging, and reaches maturity in 135 d. Its yield potential is 6,000 kg ha⁻¹ and it has intermediate threshability. Mandisovi's caryopsis is 7.64 mm long and 2.7 mm wide and its ratio of length to width is 2.82.

The endosperm contains an intermediate amylose content (23%) and low gelatinization temperature. Its protein content is 8.80% and it has a weak aroma. Mandisovi has moderate resistance to *P. oryzae* Cav.

This variety was obtained by crossing African cultivar Chocoto and H161-18 / / desc. / 80-17. Line H161-18 was developed by crossing IR1103-15-10 and Calady 40 sel. FA to obtain earliness and high protein content. The crossing was carried out by the rice program. A combination of mass and pedigree selection was used. The target area for diffusion is 32 °S near Villaguay City.

Quebracho P.A. is the first Argentine cultivar of the long-wide type, and it is aromatic and has a red pericarp. This release aimed to satisfy an increasing interest in the consumption of special rices. It is consumed as integral grain, alone or combined with similar rices of normal pericarp.

Quebracho is 0.89 m tall and resists lodging. It reaches maturity in 145 d and yields 7,000 kg ha⁻¹. It has intermediate threshability. The caryopsis is 8.1 mm long and 2.75 mm wide, and its ratio of length to width is 2.94.

For quality, it is important to mention its medium amylose content (22%) and its intermediate gelatinization temperature. Its protein content is 9.68% and it is strongly aromatic. Quebracho is resistant to *P. oryzae* Cav.

This cultivar was developed by crossing Chocoto and H161-18 / / desc. / 80-17, in a crossing carried out by the rice program. A combination of mass and pedigree selection was used. The probable target area is 32 °S near Villaguay City. ■